

Supplemental Figure 1. Analysis of the relationship between blood testosterone and corticosterone.

Analysis of the relationship between blood testosterone and corticosterone (T/C) could point to the ability of the Leydig cells to produce testosterone in stress conditions. In that respect, the relative T/C was calculated on ZT3 in control group (ZT3=1). Obtained results depicts diurnal fluctuations in blood testosterone and corticosterone; considering the analyzed time points the observed peak of fluctuations in the control group was at ZT11. Nevertheless, 1xIMO reduced T/C approximately 38-fold, depending on time of IMO event. The lowest T/C value was observed in ZT3 (T/CZT3 = 0.02), while the highest was observed in ZT11 (T/CZT11 = 0.03) (Suppl. Fig. 1A). In addition, the repeated IMO (10xIMO) profoundly reduced testosterone during passive period (Fig 1H), which resulted in a substantially decreased T/C ratio (Suppl. Fig. 1B). However, effect of 10xIMO during active period on testosterone was significantly less pronounced due to the absence of negative IMO effect on transcription of steroidogenesis-related genes (Lhcgr, Cyp11a1, Hsd3b1/2, Cyp17a1) reflecting on T/C ratio (Suppl. Fig.1B).

Wistar rats were subject to 1xIMO for three hours in four-time points (ZT0-3, ZT8-11, ZT14-17, ZT20-24) or to 10xIMO in three-time points (ZT0-3, ZT8-11, ZT20-24) during the 24h. Serum was collected for determination of corticosterone, and testosterone levels as well as testosterone/corticosterone (T/C) ratio (A: 1xIMO; B: 10xIMO). *Statistical significance between control and IMO groups for the same time point ($p < 0.05$; $n=10-12$). # Statistical significance between ZT23 and others time points ($p < 0.05$; $n=10-12$)

Supplemental Table 1.: The primers sequences used for real time PCR analysis.

Gene	GenBank accession code	Primers sequences	
<i>Gapdh</i>	NM_017008	F:5'-TGCCAAGTATGATGACATCAAGAAG-3'	R:5'-AGCCCAGGATGCCCTTTAGT-3'
<i>Cga</i>	NM_053918.2	F:5'-CAGTGTATGGGCTGTTGCTTCT-3'	R:5'-GGAACCAACATGTCTTCTTGGGA-3'
<i>Lhb</i>	NM_012858.2	F:5'-TCTTCTGATGCCACCCACTA-3'	R:5'-TATTGGGAGGGATGGTTAGAACA-3'
<i>Lhr</i>	NM_012978	F:5'-CGGGCTGGAGTCCATTCA-3'	R:5'-TTCTTTGGAGGGCAGTGTTC-3'
<i>Nr3c1</i>	NC_005117.4	F:5'-CGGTTAATCTGCACAGCCTAT-3'	R:5'-AAAATGGGTCGGTGCTTCTA-3'
<i>Star</i>	NM_031558	F:5'-AGCCAGCAGGAGAATGGAGAT-3'	R:5'-CACCTCCAGTCGGAACACCTT-3'
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	NM_017286	F:5'-GGGCAACATGGAGTCAGTTTACA-3'	R:5'-GACCCTCGCAGGAGAAGAGA-3'
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	NM_001042619.1	F:5'-GACAGGAGCAGGAGGGTTTGTGG-3'	R:5'-CTCCTTCTAACATTGTCACCTTGGCCT-3'
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	NM_012753	F:5'-GCCACGGGCGACAGAA-3'	R:5'-GCCTTTGTTGGGAAAAATCG-3'
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	NM_024392	F:5'-CCTTTGGCTTTGCCATGAGA-3'	R:5'-CAATCCATCCTGTCCAACCT-3'
<i>Clock</i>	NM_021856.1	F:5'-ACAGCCCCACTGTACAATACGA-3'	R:5'-TGCGGCATACTGGATGGAAT-3'
<i>Bmal1</i>	NM_024362.2	F:5'-AAGAGGCGTCGGGACAAAAT-3'	R:5'-TTCCGGGACATCGCATTG-3'
<i>Npas2</i>	NM_001108214.2	F:5'-GGCGCACCCCTGTGTACATTT-3'	R:5'-TCTTTCCCATTCTGCAAGTG-3'
<i>Per1</i>	NM_001034125.1	F:5'-CCTGCACACCCAGAAGGAA-3'	R:5'-GAGGTGTCAAGCCCACGAA-3'
<i>Per2</i>	NM_031678.1	F:5'-GGAAGGAGGCCCAGACGTA-3'	R:5'-TGGGTCCATTTCTGTTAGAAACA-3'
<i>Cry1</i>	NM_198750.2	F:5'-ACCATCCGCTGCGTGTACAT-3'	R:5'-AGCAAAAATCGCCACCTGTT-3'
<i>Cry2</i>	NM_133405.1	F:5'-TTCCAAGGCTTTTCAAGGA-3'	R:5'-TCCCCTTCTTTCCCAAAGG-3'
<i>Rora</i>	NM_001106834.1	F:5'-GAAGAACCACCGAGAAGATGGA-3'	R:5'-CGTCCGCATAGGGCTCTTAA-3'
<i>Rorb</i>	NM_001270958.1	F:5'-CAGGAACCGTTGCCAACAC-3'	R:5'-GGACATCTCCCAAACCTCACA-3'
<i>Rev-erba</i>	NC_005109	F:5'-GAGCATCCAGCAGAATCCA-3'	R:5'-TTGCGATTGATACGGACAATG-3'
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	NC_005114.4	F:5'-GAACGAGAATTGCTCCATCATG-3'	R:5'-CGACATTCCCACGGACAGA-3'

Primers were design by using Primer Express 3.0 software (Applied Biosystems) and full genes sequences from NCBI GenBank (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore>). F - forward, R – reverse.

Supplemental Table 2. Antibody information.

Antibody	Producer	Dilution	(kDa)	Type	Antigen Sequence	Validation
Anti-ACT	Santa Cruz Biotechnology (Heidelberg, Germany, #sc-8432)	1:800	42	Mouse Monoclonal	Human origin ACT, aa 357-375	Baburski, A. Z. et al. <i>Biol Reprod</i> 100, 1406–1415 (2019).
Anti-BMAL1	Abcam (Cambridge, UK, #ab231793)	1:800	69	Rabbit polyclonal	Rat BMAL1, aa 1-200	Chen, G. et al. <i>Frontiers in Pharmacology</i> 11, (2020). Baburski, A. Z. et al. <i>Exp. Gerontol.</i> 73, 5–13 (2016).
Anti-PER1	Abcam (Cambridge, UK, #ab3443)	1:500	136	Rabbit polyclonal	Mouse PER1, aa 39-51	Baburski, A. Z. et al. <i>Biol Reprod</i> 100, 1406–1415 (2019).
Anti-GR (BuGR2)	Thermo Fisher Scientific (Massachusetts, USA, #MA1-510)	1:1000	97	Mouse Monoclonal	Partially purified rat GR	Medar, M. et al. <i>Mol. and Cell. Endocrinol.</i> 538, 111469 (2021). Baker G. et al. <i>Cancer Menag. Res.</i> 361, (2015).

Supplemental Table 3. Rhythm parameters of the data detected in the control group shown in Figures 2 and 3: variations in corticosterone, glucose, and testosterone in the blood, as well as gene expression in pituitary and Leydig cells. The blood corticosterone, glucose, testosterone levels, and gene expression were estimated at four-time points (ZT0-3, ZT8-11, ZT14-17, and ZT20-23; ZT0 is a time when the light turned on). Pituitary and Leydig cells from different time points were used for mRNA isolation, followed by RQ-PCR gene expression analysis using $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$ method normalized on Control ZT03. Presented data were obtained by the Cosinor method. The bolded items show a rhythmic fluctuation in expression ($p < 0.05$).

	Group	p	Mesor	Amplitude	Acrophase
Corticosterone (nmol/L)	Control	0.00001	56.44899	22.1387	10.91316
Glucose (mmol/L)	Control	0.053450	6.991290	0.50628	9.121611
Testosterone (ng/mL)	Control	0.000010	4.126340	2.709868	10.392056
Cga	Control	0.000010	2.539760	1.344414	15.387778
Cgb	Control	0.000010	1.169380	0.414669	18.451450
<i>Lhcgr</i>	Control	0.080400			
Nr3c1	Control	0.000050	1.103210	0.325498	10.376503
Star	Control	0.040120	0.996430	0.295860	3.168410
Cyp11a1	Control	0.000120	0.801560	0.394170	6.150374
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	Control	0.143420			
Hsd17b4	Control	0.000005	0.830570	0.115314	2.849319
Cyp17a1	Control	0.000050	0.705630	0.347059	6.061222
Bmal1	Control	0.000001	0.560690	0.408230	1.909399
<i>Clock</i>	Control	0.361930			
<i>Npas2</i>	Control	0.060000			
Per1	Control	0.000190	1.165	0.5610238	11.587508
Per2	Control	0.000010	1.802710	0.881767	12.759931
Cry1	Control	0.000050	1.868170	1.461789	18.230596
Cry2	Control	0.00805	0.748620	0.350629	9.164588
Rev-erba	Control	0.000960	1.005010	0.334595	7.523166
Rev-erbb	Control	0.000001	0.885530	0.659719	7.522000
<i>Rora</i>	Control	0.585500			
Rorb	Control	0.000150	0.795850	0.795850	8.297699

Supplemental Table 4. Variables loadings of relative gene expression from principal component analysis. In this and following Tables data calculated in PC are obtained by $2^{\Delta(-\Delta\Delta CT)}$ method normalized on Control ZT03. PC-principalcomponent.

	PC1	PC2	PC3
<i>Lhgcr</i>	-0.07152	0.491352	0.642671
<i>Star</i>	-0.50755	-0.39841	0.235081
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	-0.52355	-0.09524	-0.20899
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	-0.57174	-0.01094	-0.17463
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	0.080507	-0.59493	0.623839
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	0.36029	-0.48653	-0.26146

Supplemental Table 5. Variables loadings of relative gene expression from principal component analysis. PC-principalcomponent.

	PC1	PC2	PC3
<i>Lhgcr</i>	0.52014	-0.20273	-0.15335
<i>Star</i>	0.335387	0.467236	0.572887
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	0.483617	0.024252	0.053696
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	0.451647	0.057046	0.227036
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	-0.02927	0.84484	-0.47888
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	0.422188	-0.15164	-0.60377

Supplemental Table 6. Variables loadings of relative gene expression from principal component analysis. PC-principalcomponent.

	PC1	PC2	PC3
<i>Lhgcr</i>	-0.4523	-0.0326	-0.0254
<i>Star</i>	-0.4271	-0.3530	-0.2330
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	-0.4482	0.0260	-0.4677
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	-0.4556	-0.0336	-0.0369
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	-0.1510	0.9317	-0.1378
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	0.4264	-0.0669	-0.8402

Supplemental Table 7. Variables loadings of relative gene expression from principal component analysis. PC-principalcomponent.

	PC1	PC2	PC3
<i>Clock</i>	-0.25404	0.068451	-0.49355
<i>Npas2</i>	-0.32152	0.206485	0.186631
<i>Bmal1</i>	0.123285	0.313721	-0.56317
<i>Per1</i>	-0.39623	0.214477	0.189347
<i>Per2</i>	-0.35392	0.040101	0.373339
<i>Cry1</i>	0.297963	0.188317	0.431501
<i>Cry2</i>	-0.36158	0.360493	-0.05679
<i>Rev-erba</i>	-0.03673	-0.48991	0.019381
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	-0.3241	-0.36745	0.038873
<i>Rora</i>	-0.10154	-0.51169	-0.1372
<i>Rorb</i>	-0.44544	-0.06615	-0.13804

Supplemental Table 8. Variables loadings of relative gene expression from principal component analysis. PC-principalcomponent.

	PC1	PC2	PC3
<i>Clock</i>	0.29394	0.252515	-0.012
<i>Npas2</i>	0.418848	0.12091	-0.16573
<i>Bmal1</i>	-0.01235	-0.26517	0.64281
<i>Per1</i>	-0.39162	0.287647	0.001399
<i>Per2</i>	-0.21037	-0.22199	-0.58538
<i>Cry1</i>	-0.28311	-0.39929	-0.19258
<i>Cry2</i>	-0.34858	0.323843	0.132776
<i>Rev-erba</i>	-0.30645	-0.04314	-0.24555
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	-0.36315	0.251142	0.082741
<i>Rora</i>	0.291554	0.350113	-0.30549
<i>Rorb</i>	-0.16715	0.517165	0.036471

Supplemental Table 9. Variables loadings of relative gene expression from principal component analysis. PC-principalcomponent.

	PC1	PC2	PC3
<i>Clock</i>	-0.17029	0.417045	0.266498
<i>Npas2</i>	0.360635	-0.2167	-0.15463
<i>Bmal1</i>	0.360635	-0.2167	-0.15463
<i>Per1</i>	0.151323	-0.35597	0.881661
<i>Per2</i>	-0.36249	0.201738	-0.05567
<i>Cry1</i>	-0.39712	-0.03046	0.123363
<i>Cry2</i>	-0.26365	-0.34202	-0.0533
<i>Rev-erba</i>	0.264825	0.358734	0.175803
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	-0.13708	-0.43948	-0.21223
<i>Rora</i>	0.272342	0.353571	-0.06742
<i>Rorb</i>	0.407769	0.001224	-0.04669

1xIMO Source data

The blood corticosterone, glucose, testosterone levels, and gene expression were estimated at four-time points (ZT0-3, ZT8-11, ZT14-17, and ZT20-23; ZT0 is a time when the light turned on). Pituitary and Leydig cells from different time points were used for mRNA isolation, followed by RQ-PCR gene expression analysis using the 2^{-ΔΔCT} method normalized on Control ZT03.

Hormone/Gene	Treatment	Zt	Value	Unit
Corticosterone	control	3	49.63	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	3	39.10	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	3	59.14	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	3	30.63	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	3	48.63	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	11	78.81	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	11	78.92	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	11	78.90	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	11	80.81	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	11	76.81	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	17	55.48	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	17	56.00	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	17	55.59	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	17	51.48	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	17	59.48	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	23	25.00	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	23	45.00	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	23	41.28	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	23	21.30	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	23	41.32	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	3	201.80	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	3	205.80	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	3	195.80	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	3	196.00	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	3	199.54	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	11	184.20	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	11	186.00	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	11	186.10	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	11	188.20	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	11	180.20	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	17	200.80	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	17	202.10	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	17	202.46	nmol/L

Corticosterone	imo	17	208.80	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	17	192.80	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	23	225.00	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	23	226.00	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	23	222.00	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	23	215.00	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	23	205.00	nmol/L
Glucose	control	3	6.40	mmol/L
Glucose	control	3	6.18	mmol/L
Glucose	control	3	8.41	mmol/L
Glucose	control	3	7.15	mmol/L
Glucose	control	3	6.85	mmol/L
Glucose	control	11	7.10	mmol/L
Glucose	control	11	7.34	mmol/L
Glucose	control	11	8.01	mmol/L
Glucose	control	11	6.93	mmol/L
Glucose	control	11	7.73	mmol/L
Glucose	control	17	6.38	mmol/L
Glucose	control	17	6.82	mmol/L
Glucose	control	17	6.31	mmol/L
Glucose	control	17	7.58	mmol/L
Glucose	control	17	6.77	mmol/L
Glucose	control	23	6.49	mmol/L
Glucose	control	23	6.57	mmol/L
Glucose	control	23	6.45	mmol/L
Glucose	control	23	6.07	mmol/L
Glucose	control	23	7.01	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	3	10.25	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	3	9.17	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	3	7.75	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	3	11.23	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	3	10.09	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	11	8.57	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	11	7.28	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	11	8.37	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	11	8.39	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	11	8.58	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	17	7.49	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	17	6.38	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	17	7.27	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	17	8.30	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	17	6.59	mmol/L

Glucose	imo	23	8.53	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	23	8.42	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	23	9.70	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	23	7.87	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	23	9.48	mmol/L
Testosterone	control	3	2.40	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	3	2.38	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	3	3.20	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	3	1.60	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	3	2.43	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	11	6.75	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	11	7.10	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	11	6.75	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	11	7.25	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	11	8.75	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	17	4.25	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	17	3.97	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	17	2.05	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	17	2.45	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	17	2.48	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	23	1.80	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	23	3.67	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	23	2.25	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	23	1.79	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	23	2.23	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	3	0.49	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	3	0.62	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	3	0.42	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	3	0.82	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	3	0.53	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	11	0.96	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	11	0.95	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	11	1.20	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	11	1.09	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	11	0.54	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	17	0.60	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	17	1.03	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	17	0.64	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	17	0.74	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	17	1.24	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	23	0.61	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	23	1.00	ng/mL

Testosterone	imo	23	0.99	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	23	0.98	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	23	0.52	ng/mL
<i>Cga</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	3	1.03	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	11	3.20	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	11	3.21	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	11	3.21	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	11	3.25	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	11	3.26	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	17	3.60	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	17	3.74	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	17	3.74	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	17	3.45	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	17	3.44	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	23	2.27	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	23	2.20	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	23	2.14	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	23	2.16	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	23	2.35	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	3	1.92	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	3	1.92	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	3	2.14	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	3	2.21	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	3	1.84	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	11	2.50	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	11	2.52	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	11	2.52	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	11	2.65	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	11	2.54	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	17	2.32	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	17	2.29	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	17	2.34	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	17	2.32	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	17	2.32	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	23	1.98	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	23	1.98	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	23	1.98	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	23	1.92	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)

<i>Cga</i>	imo	23	1.94	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	11	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	11	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	11	0.95	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	11	0.94	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	11	0.91	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	17	1.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	17	1.66	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	17	1.61	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	17	1.63	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	17	1.63	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	23	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	23	1.23	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	23	1.24	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	23	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	23	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	3	0.96	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	3	0.97	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	3	0.95	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	11	0.87	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	11	0.84	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	11	0.86	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	11	0.85	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	11	0.86	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	17	2.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	17	1.60	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	17	1.57	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	17	1.59	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	17	2.22	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	23	2.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	23	2.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	23	2.23	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	23	2.27	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	23	2.27	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	3	1.03	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	3	1.03	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	3	1.09	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	3	0.93	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	11	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	11	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	11	1.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	11	1.37	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	11	1.46	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	17	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	17	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	11	0.97	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	17	0.97	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	17	0.94	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	23	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	23	0.86	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	23	1.06	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	23	1.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	23	1.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	3	0.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	3	0.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	3	0.35	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	3	0.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	3	0.30	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	11	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	11	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	11	0.61	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	11	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	11	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	17	1.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	17	1.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	17	1.13	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	17	1.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	17	1.07	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	23	1.06	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	23	1.04	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	23	1.04	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	23	1.03	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	23	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	3	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Star</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	3	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	11	1.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	11	1.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	11	1.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	11	1.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	11	1.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	17	0.58	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	17	0.30	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	17	0.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	17	0.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	17	0.30	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	23	1.47	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	23	1.49	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	23	1.49	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	23	1.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	23	1.43	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	3	0.30	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	3	0.30	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	3	0.30	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	3	0.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	3	0.30	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	11	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	11	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	11	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	11	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	11	0.73	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	17	0.36	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	17	0.36	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	17	0.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	17	0.33	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	17	0.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	23	0.43	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	23	0.43	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	23	0.47	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	23	0.54	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	23	0.47	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	3	1.02	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	11	0.84	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	11	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	11	1.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	11	1.17	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	11	1.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	17	0.40	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	17	0.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	17	0.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	17	0.37	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	17	0.23	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	23	0.67	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	23	0.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	23	0.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	23	0.81	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	23	0.90	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	3	0.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	3	0.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	3	0.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	3	0.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	3	0.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	11	0.97	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	11	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	11	0.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	11	1.05	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	11	0.90	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	17	0.47	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	17	0.49	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	17	0.47	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	17	0.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	17	0.88	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	23	0.91	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	23	0.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	23	0.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	23	0.91	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	23	0.90	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	3	1.04	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	3	0.97	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	11	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	11	1.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	11	1.20	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	11	1.12	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	11	1.06	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	17	1.15	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	17	1.15	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	17	1.14	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	17	1.14	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	17	1.23	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	23	1.20	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	23	1.22	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	23	1.22	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	23	1.24	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	23	1.21	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	3	0.31	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	3	0.31	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	3	0.21	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	3	0.20	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	3	0.31	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	11	0.67	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	11	0.67	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	11	0.67	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	11	0.69	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	11	0.67	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	17	1.17	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	17	1.17	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	17	1.17	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	17	1.14	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	17	1.07	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	23	1.00	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	23	1.00	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	23	1.00	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	23	1.00	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	23	1.18	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	3	1.01	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	3	1.05	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	11	0.98	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	11	0.78	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	11	0.62	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	11	0.88	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)

<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	11	0.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	17	0.38	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	17	0.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	17	0.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	17	0.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	17	0.54	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	23	0.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	23	0.53	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	23	0.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	23	0.61	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	23	0.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	3	0.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	3	0.68	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	3	0.70	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	3	0.71	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	3	0.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	11	0.64	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	11	0.63	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	11	0.65	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	11	0.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	11	0.80	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	17	0.33	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	17	0.34	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	17	0.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	17	0.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	17	0.35	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	23	0.87	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	23	0.88	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	23	0.88	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	23	0.91	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	23	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	11	0.74	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	11	0.74	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	11	0.74	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	11	0.73	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	11	0.71	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	17	0.77	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	17	0.77	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	17	0.76	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	17	0.79	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	17	0.79	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	23	0.60	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	23	0.61	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	23	0.91	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	23	0.60	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	control	23	0.60	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	3	0.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	3	0.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	3	0.44	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	3	0.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	3	0.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	11	0.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	11	0.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	11	0.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	11	0.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	11	0.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	17	0.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	17	0.44	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	17	0.40	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	17	0.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	17	0.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	23	0.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	23	0.86	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	23	0.86	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	23	0.89	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	imo	23	0.87	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	3	0.95	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	11	0.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	11	0.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	11	0.22	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	11	0.27	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	11	0.25	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	17	0.25	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	17	0.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	17	0.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Bmal1</i>	control	17	0.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	17	0.40	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	23	0.95	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	23	0.81	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	23	0.81	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	23	0.83	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	23	0.67	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	3	1.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	3	1.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	3	1.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	3	1.59	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	3	1.68	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	11	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	11	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	11	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	11	0.85	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	11	0.80	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	17	0.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	17	0.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	17	0.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	17	0.45	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	17	0.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	23	1.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	23	1.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	23	1.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	23	1.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	23	1.56	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	3	0.97	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	3	1.09	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	11	0.83	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	11	0.83	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	11	0.84	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	11	0.82	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	11	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	17	0.65	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	17	0.66	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	17	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	17	0.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	17	0.91	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	23	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	23	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Clock</i>	control	23	1.02	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	23	1.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	23	1.06	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	3	0.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	3	0.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	3	0.56	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	3	0.59	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	3	0.59	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	11	1.35	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	11	0.71	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	11	0.71	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	11	0.34	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	11	0.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	17	0.60	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	17	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	17	0.60	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	17	1.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	17	1.09	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	23	0.61	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	23	0.61	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	23	0.60	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	23	0.60	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	23	0.91	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	3	1.05	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	3	1.05	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	3	1.05	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	3	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	3	0.95	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	11	0.95	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	11	0.95	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	11	0.95	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	11	0.86	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	11	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	17	0.82	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	17	0.82	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	17	0.85	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	17	0.84	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	17	0.86	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	23	0.67	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	23	0.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	23	0.79	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	23	1.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Npas2</i>	control	23	1.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	3	0.93	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	11	0.91	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	11	0.91	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	11	0.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	11	0.90	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	11	0.91	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	17	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	17	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	17	1.08	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	17	1.09	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	17	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	23	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	23	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	23	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	23	0.73	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	23	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	3	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	3	0.93	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	11	1.58	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	11	1.58	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	11	1.73	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	11	1.73	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	11	1.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	17	1.40	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	17	1.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	17	1.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	17	1.44	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	17	1.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	23	0.44	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	23	0.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	23	0.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	23	0.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	23	0.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	3	6.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Per1</i>	imo	3	6.73	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	3	6.73	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	3	6.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	3	6.49	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	11	4.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	11	4.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	11	4.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	11	3.93	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	11	4.02	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	17	4.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	17	4.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	17	4.40	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	17	4.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	17	4.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	23	6.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	23	6.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	23	6.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	23	6.45	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	23	6.39	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	3	1.05	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	3	1.05	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	11	2.71	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	11	2.71	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	11	2.70	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	11	2.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	11	2.73	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	17	2.15	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	17	2.15	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	17	2.15	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	17	2.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	17	2.13	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	23	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	23	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	23	1.03	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	23	1.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	23	1.22	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	3	4.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	3	4.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	3	4.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Per2</i>	imo	3	3.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	3	3.68	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	11	2.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	11	2.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	11	2.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	11	2.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	11	2.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	17	1.75	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	17	1.75	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	17	1.75	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	17	1.74	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	17	1.73	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	23	1.85	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	23	1.85	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	23	1.85	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	23	1.82	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	23	1.80	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	3	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	3	0.85	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	3	1.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	11	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	11	0.89	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	11	0.89	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	11	0.89	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	11	0.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	17	3.49	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	17	3.49	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	17	3.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	17	3.27	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	17	3.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	23	2.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	23	2.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	23	2.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	23	2.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	23	2.57	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	3	2.45	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	3	2.45	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	3	2.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	3	2.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	3	2.38	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

Cry1	imo	11	1.43	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry1	imo	11	1.43	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry1	imo	11	1.43	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry1	imo	11	1.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry1	imo	11	2.35	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry1	imo	17	4.44	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry1	imo	17	3.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry1	imo	17	3.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry1	imo	17	3.23	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry1	imo	17	2.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry1	imo	23	4.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry1	imo	23	4.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry1	imo	23	4.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry1	imo	23	4.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry1	imo	23	4.38	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	3	0.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	3	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	3	1.04	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	11	0.75	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	11	0.76	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	11	0.76	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	11	0.94	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	11	1.26	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	17	0.70	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	17	0.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	17	0.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	17	0.89	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	17	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	23	0.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	23	0.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	23	0.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	23	0.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	control	23	0.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	imo	3	1.23	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	imo	3	1.23	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	imo	3	1.23	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	imo	3	1.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	imo	3	1.02	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	imo	11	0.37	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
Cry2	imo	11	0.38	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Cry2</i>	imo	11	0.38	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	11	0.40	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	11	0.57	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	17	0.38	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	17	0.39	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	17	0.38	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	17	0.57	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	17	0.93	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	23	1.17	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	23	1.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	23	1.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	23	2.58	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	23	2.45	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	3	1.2	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	3	0.77	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	3	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	11	1.25	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	11	1.25	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	11	1.3	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	11	1.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	11	1.2	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	17	0.55	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	17	0.54	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	17	0.54	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	17	0.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	17	0.79	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	23	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	23	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	23	1.13	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	23	0.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	23	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	3	0.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	3	0.61	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	3	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	3	0.64	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	3	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	11	0.61	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	11	0.59	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	11	0.59	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	11	0.63	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	11	0.63	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	17	0.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	17	0.23	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	17	0.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	17	0.24	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	17	0.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	23	0.71	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	23	0.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	23	0.68	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	23	0.65	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	23	0.67	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	3	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	11	1.36	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	11	1.36	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	11	1.36	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	11	1.44	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	11	1.39	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	17	0.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	17	0.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	17	0.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	17	0.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	17	0.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	23	0.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	23	0.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	23	0.64	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	23	0.78	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	23	0.78	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	3	0.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	3	0.70	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	3	0.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	3	0.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	3	0.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	11	0.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	11	0.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	11	0.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	11	0.75	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	11	0.75	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	17	0.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	17	0.32	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	17	0.32	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	17	0.48	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	17	0.36	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	23	0.40	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	23	0.40	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	23	0.42	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	23	0.40	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	23	0.50	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	3	1.10	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	3	0.82	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	3	0.96	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	11	1.21	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	11	1.08	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	11	1.07	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	11	1.13	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	11	1.14	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	17	0.92	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	17	0.92	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	17	0.99	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	17	0.77	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	17	0.71	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	23	0.74	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	23	0.64	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	23	0.72	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	23	1.25	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	23	1.24	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	3	1.24	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	3	1.19	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	3	1.16	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	3	1.17	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	3	1.17	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	11	1.00	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	11	0.98	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	11	0.98	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	11	0.00	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	11	0.96	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	17	1.80	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	17	1.80	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	17	1.80	2 [^] (- $\Delta\Delta$ CT)

<i>Rora</i>	imo	17	2.27	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	17	1.75	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	23	1.15	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	23	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	23	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	23	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	23	1.23	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	3	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	11	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	11	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	11	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	11	1.53	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	11	1.36	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	17	0.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	17	0.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	17	0.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	17	0.35	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	17	0.37	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	23	0.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	23	0.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	23	0.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	23	0.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	23	0.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	3	1.24	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	3	1.24	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	3	1.24	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	3	1.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	3	1.16	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	11	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	11	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	11	1.02	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	11	1.03	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	11	0.96	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	17	1.80	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	17	1.80	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	17	1.80	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	17	2.27	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	17	1.75	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Rorb</i>	imo	23	1.15	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	23	1.15	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	23	1.15	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	23	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	23	1.23	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	3	1.06	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	3	1.05	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	3	1.05	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	3	0.95	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	11	1.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	11	1.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	11	1.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	11	1.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	11	1.18	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	17	1.05	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	17	1.05	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	17	1.05	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	17	1.08	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	17	1.06	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	23	0.82	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	23	0.61	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	23	0.84	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	3	0.95	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	3	0.96	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	3	0.82	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	3	0.82	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	3	0.66	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	11	0.55	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	11	0.64	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	11	0.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	11	0.80	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	17	1.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	17	1.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	17	1.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	17	1.27	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	17	0.94	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	23	0.95	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	23	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	23	0.96	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	23	1.09	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	23	1.09	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

10xIMO Source data

The blood corticosterone, glucose, testosterone levels, and gene expression were estimated at three-time points (ZT0-3, ZT8-11 and ZT20-23; ZT0 is a time when the light turned on). Pituitary and Leydig cells from different time points were used for mRNA isolation, followed by RQ-PCR gene expression analysis using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$ method normalized on Control ZT03.

Hormone/Gene	Treatment	Zt	Value	Unit
Corticosterone	control	3	15.12	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	3	15.59	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	3	25.94	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	3	15.111	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	3	16.46	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	11	36.6	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	11	44.1	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	11	32.19	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	11	36.17	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	11	38.06	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	23	20.1	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	23	20.5	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	23	20.29	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	23	18.72	nmol/L
Corticosterone	control	23	22.4	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	3	40.04	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	3	42.97	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	3	40.19	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	3	50.46	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	3	45.73	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	11	55.6	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	11	58.22	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	11	50.14	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	11	56.02	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	11	21.35	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	23	35.65	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	23	49.44	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	23	40.03	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	23	30.62	nmol/L
Corticosterone	imo	23	43.87	nmol/L
Glucose	control	3	5.12	mmol/L
Glucose	control	3	5.12	mmol/L
Glucose	control	3	5.16	mmol/L

Glucose	control	3	5.45	mmol/L
Glucose	control	3	5.22	mmol/L
Glucose	control	11	7.4	mmol/L
Glucose	control	11	7.23	mmol/L
Glucose	control	11	7.32	mmol/L
Glucose	control	11	7.78	mmol/L
Glucose	control	11	7.12	mmol/L
Glucose	control	23	4.21	mmol/L
Glucose	control	23	4.11	mmol/L
Glucose	control	23	4.3	mmol/L
Glucose	control	23	4.12	mmol/L
Glucose	control	23	4.23	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	3	8.93	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	3	8.65	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	3	8.45	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	3	8.89	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	3	8.85	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	11	8.79	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	11	8.69	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	11	9.11	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	11	9.23	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	11	9.19	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	23	9.64	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	23	9.66	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	23	9.87	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	23	9.36	mmol/L
Glucose	imo	23	9.67	mmol/L
Testosterone	control	3	4.94	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	3	4.48	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	3	3.9	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	3	2.63	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	3	11.9	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	11	6.75	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	11	7.10	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	11	6.75	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	11	7.25	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	11	8.75	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	23	0.562	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	23	2.65	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	23	5.45	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	23	3.03	ng/mL
Testosterone	control	23	3.66	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	3	0.394	ng/mL

Testosterone	imo	3	0.255	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	3	0.296	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	3	0.76	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	3	0.199	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	11	0.157	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	11	0.238	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	11	0.333	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	11	0.143	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	11	0.295	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	23	0.921	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	23	0.469	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	23	1.21	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	23	2.77	ng/mL
Testosterone	imo	23	0.8	ng/mL
<i>Cga</i>	control	3	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	3	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	3	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	3	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	3	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	11	4.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	11	4.13	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	11	4.13	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	11	4.02	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	11	4.02	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	23	2.1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	23	2.1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	23	2.2	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	23	2.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	control	23	2.15	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	3	1.5	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	3	1.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	3	1.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	3	1.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	3	1.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	11	2.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	11	2.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	11	2.18	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	11	2.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	11	2.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	23	1.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	23	1.95	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	23	1.93	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cga</i>	imo	23	1.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Cga</i>	imo	23	1.91	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	3	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	3	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	3	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	3	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	11	2.1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	11	2.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	11	2.13	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	11	2.09	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	11	2.07	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	23	0.84	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	23	0.82	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	23	0.81	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	23	0.81	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	control	23	0.81	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	3	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	3	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	3	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	3	1.25	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	3	1.24	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	11	0.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	11	0.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	11	0.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	11	0.49	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	11	0.49	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	23	0.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	23	0.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	23	0.47	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	23	0.46	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhb</i>	imo	23	0.46	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	3	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	3	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	3	0.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	3	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	11	1.5	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	11	1.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	11	1.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	11	1.5	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	11	1.5	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	23	0.75	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	23	0.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	23	0.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	23	0.75	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	control	23	0.75	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	3	0.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	3	0.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	3	0.56	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	3	0.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	3	0.55	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	11	0.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	11	0.4	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	11	0.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	11	0.39	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	11	0.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	23	0.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	23	0.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	23	0.5	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	23	0.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Lhcgr</i>	imo	23	0.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	3	1.02	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	3	0.96	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	11	1.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	11	1.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	11	1.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	11	1.13	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	11	1.04	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	23	1.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	23	1.28	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	23	1.24	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	23	1.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	control	23	1.30	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	3	0.60	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	3	0.61	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	3	0.61	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	3	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	3	0.63	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	11	0.33	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	11	0.33	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	11	0.33	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	11	0.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	11	0.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Star</i>	imo	23	0.70	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	23	0.76	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	23	0.76	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	23	0.87	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Star</i>	imo	23	0.87	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	3	0.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	3	1.02	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	11	2.60	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	11	2.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	11	2.59	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	11	2.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	11	2.49	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	23	3.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	23	3.08	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	23	3.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	23	3.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	control	23	3.13	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	3	0.96	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	3	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	3	1.03	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	11	1.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	11	1.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	11	1.49	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	11	1.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	11	1.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	23	3.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	23	3.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	23	3.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	23	3.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	11	1.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	11	1.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	11	1.30	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	11	1.30	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	11	1.06	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	23	1.44	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	23	1.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	23	1.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	23	1.35	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	control	23	1.30	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	3	0.80	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	3	0.81	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	3	0.81	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	3	0.80	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	3	0.90	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	11	0.71	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	11	0.71	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	11	0.70	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	11	0.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	11	0.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	23	1.24	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	23	1.24	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	23	1.23	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	23	1.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd3b1/2</i>	imo	23	1.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	imo	23	2.95	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	11	0.38	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	11	0.34	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	11	0.34	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	11	0.36	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	11	0.33	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	23	0.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	23	0.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	23	0.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	23	0.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	control	23	0.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	3	0.43	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	3	0.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	3	0.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	3	0.44	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	3	0.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	11	0.25	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	11	0.24	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	11	0.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	11	0.22	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	11	0.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	23	0.59	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	23	0.61	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	23	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	23	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cyp17a1</i>	imo	23	0.63	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	control	3	0.94	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	control	3	0.96	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	control	11	0.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	control	11	0.33	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	control	11	0.33	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	control	11	0.40	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	control	11	0.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	control	23	0.81	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	control	23	0.81	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	control	23	0.80	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	control	23	0.74	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	control	23	0.75	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	imo	3	0.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	imo	3	0.34	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	imo	3	0.34	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	imo	3	0.33	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	imo	3	0.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	imo	11	0.26	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	imo	11	0.25	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	imo	11	0.25	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	imo	11	0.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	imo	11	0.22	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	imo	23	0.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	imo	23	0.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	imo	23	0.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	imo	23	0.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Hsd17b/4</i>	imo	23	0.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	3	0.97	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Bmal1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	11	0.81	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	11	0.79	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	11	0.78	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	11	0.80	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	11	0.77	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	23	1.70	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	23	1.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	23	1.68	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	23	1.73	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	control	23	1.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	3	1.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	3	1.09	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	3	1.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	3	1.13	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	3	1.04	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	11	0.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	11	0.49	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	11	0.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	11	0.54	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	11	0.55	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	23	1.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	23	1.53	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	23	1.53	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	23	1.58	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Bmal1</i>	imo	23	1.58	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	11	1.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	11	1.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	11	1.23	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	11	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	11	1.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	23	1.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	23	1.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	23	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	23	1.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	control	23	1.13	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	3	0.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	3	0.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Clock</i>	imo	3	0.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	3	0.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	3	0.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	11	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	11	1.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	11	1.18	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	11	1.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	11	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	23	1.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	23	1.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	23	1.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	23	1.16	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Clock</i>	imo	23	1.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	3	1.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	3	1.02	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	11	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	11	1.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	11	1.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	11	1.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	11	1.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	23	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	23	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	23	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	23	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	control	23	0.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	3	1.08	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	11	2.64	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	11	2.64	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	11	2.45	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	11	2.46	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	11	2.45	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	23	1.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	23	1.15	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	23	1.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	23	1.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Npas2</i>	imo	23	1.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Per1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	11	2.77	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	11	2.78	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	11	2.78	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	11	2.89	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	11	2.89	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	23	3.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	23	3.49	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	23	3.36	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	23	3.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	control	23	3.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	3	1.89	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	3	1.70	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	3	1.84	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	3	1.87	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	3	1.81	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	11	4.59	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	11	4.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	11	4.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	11	4.72	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	11	4.64	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	23	4.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	23	4.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	23	4.26	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	23	4.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per1</i>	imo	23	4.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	3	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	11	3.34	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	11	3.26	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	11	3.24	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	11	3.27	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	11	3.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	23	2.58	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	23	2.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	23	2.39	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Per2</i>	control	23	2.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	control	23	2.63	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	3	0.68	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	3	0.68	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	3	0.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	3	0.68	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	3	0.59	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	11	4.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	11	4.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	11	4.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	11	4.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	11	4.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	23	2.17	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	23	2.16	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	23	2.16	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	23	2.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Per2</i>	imo	23	2.58	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	3	0.86	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	11	1.49	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	11	1.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	11	1.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	11	1.44	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	11	1.42	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	23	2.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	23	2.39	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	23	2.34	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	23	2.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	control	23	2.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	3	1.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	3	1.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	3	1.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	11	2.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	11	2.05	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	11	2.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	11	2.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	11	2.02	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	23	2.30	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Cry1</i>	imo	23	2.34	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	23	2.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	23	2.36	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry1</i>	imo	23	2.36	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	control	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	control	11	2.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	control	11	2.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	control	11	2.13	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	control	11	2.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	control	11	2.05	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	control	23	2.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	control	23	2.24	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	control	23	2.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	control	23	2.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	control	23	2.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	3	1.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	3	1.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	3	1.13	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	3	0.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	3	1.05	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	11	2.25	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	11	2.24	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	11	2.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	11	2.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	11	2.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	23	1.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	23	1.68	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	23	1.68	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	23	1.67	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Cry2</i>	imo	23	1.70	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	3	0.97	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	11	1.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	11	1.23	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	11	1.24	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	11	1.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	11	1.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	23	0.89	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	23	0.84	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	23	0.85	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	23	0.79	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	23	0.85	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	3	0.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	3	0.22	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	3	0.24	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	3	0.30	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	3	0.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	11	0.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	11	0.25	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	11	0.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	11	0.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	11	0.31	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	23	1.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	23	1.18	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	23	1.15	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	23	1.17	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	imo	23	1.17	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	3	1.04	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	3	1.04	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	11	1.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	11	1.49	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	11	1.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	11	1.51	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	11	1.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	23	0.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	control	23	0.90	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	23	0.89	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	23	0.91	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erba</i>	control	23	0.89	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	3	1.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	3	1.14	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	3	1.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	11	1.50	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	11	1.45	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	11	1.49	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	11	1.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	11	1.52	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	23	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	23	0.56	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	23	0.57	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	23	0.58	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rev-erbb</i>	imo	23	0.59	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	3	0.98	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	11	1.10	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	11	1.11	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	11	1.12	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	11	1.05	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	11	1.09	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	23	0.64	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	23	0.65	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	23	0.65	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	23	0.70	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	control	23	0.68	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	3	0.66	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	3	0.69	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	3	0.65	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	3	0.68	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	3	0.78	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	11	0.40	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	11	0.46	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	11	0.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	11	0.48	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	11	0.45	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	23	1.20	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	23	1.17	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	23	1.19	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	23	1.18	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rora</i>	imo	23	1.28	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	3	0.99	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	3	0.89	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	3	1.00	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Rorb</i>	control	11	1.64	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	11	1.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	11	1.63	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	11	1.65	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	11	1.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	23	0.93	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	23	0.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	23	0.91	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	23	0.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	control	23	0.91	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	3	1.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	3	1.39	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	3	1.36	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	3	1.40	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	3	1.45	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	11	0.62	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	11	0.61	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	11	0.65	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	11	0.65	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	11	0.63	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	23	1.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	23	1.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	23	1.28	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	23	1.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Rorb</i>	imo	23	1.32	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	3	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	3	1.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	3	0.92	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	3	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	3	1	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	11	1.3	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	11	1.26	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	11	1.22	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	11	1.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	11	1.29	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	23	0.79	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	23	0.78	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	23	0.78	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	23	0.82	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	control	23	0.81	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	3	1.4	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	3	1.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	3	1.41	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)

<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	3	1.45	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	3	1.35	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	11	2	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	11	2.02	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	11	2.02	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	11	2.01	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	11	2.02	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	23	1.21	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	23	1.22	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	23	1.2	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	23	1.2	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)
<i>Nr3c1</i>	imo	23	1.2	2 [^] (-ΔΔCT)